

Research Article

Encapsulation of molecular chromophores in phosphate glass towards improved stability against photodegradation

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A B S T R A C T

In this study molecular porphyrin chromophores have been successfully vitrified in AgPO₃ glass via a simple, low-temperature, post-melting encapsulation procedure. Their controlled incorporation within the phosphate glass network results to enhanced stability against visible light exposure while preserved their structural integrity. This simple method ensures the optical and electronic properties of porphyrins remain intact, rendering the developed composite porphyrin-glasses suitable for light-harvesting and photocatalytic applications. The AgPO₃ glass matrix acts as a protective barrier, shielding porphyrins from environmental factors. This scalable, cost-effective technique eliminates the need for chemical modifications or anchoring groups, offering a robust pathway for integrating molecular chromophores into transparent optical media for advanced functional applications.

1. Introduction

In recent years, porphyrins, renowned for their unique structural features and redox properties, have found wide-ranging applications across various fields [1,2]. In catalysis [3], porphyrins serve as efficient photosensitizers [4,5] and catalysts in a myriad of reactions like water splitting, H₂ generation [6,7], alcohol oxidation [8], water oxidation [9], CO₂ reduction [10,11] and more. Beyond catalysis, porphyrins have been utilized in areas such as photovoltaics [12,13], sensing, drug delivery [14], photodynamic therapy [15] and wound healing [16], where their exceptional light-absorption and electron-transfer capabilities are harnessed for diverse functionalities [17,18].

Despite their remarkable properties and widespread utility, porphyrins often encounter structural and optical stability challenges when employed in applications such as catalysis, notably as photosensitizers [19]. One primary issue stems from their susceptibility to photodegradation upon prolonged exposure to light [20], which can lead to the loss of the overall catalytic activity and efficiency over time. Additionally, the interaction of porphyrins with reactive intermediates or harsh reaction conditions can induce structural alterations or chemical degradation, further compromising their stability and durability [21]. Moreover, in catalytic environments, porphyrins may undergo

undesired side reactions such as demetallation, diminishing their effectiveness and limiting their recovery and reuse [22]. These stability issues necessitate careful design strategies and the development of robust support materials or protective coatings to enhance the durability and performance of porphyrin-based catalytic systems, and thus, render them attractive candidates in practical large-scale applications [23]. As for instance, the introduction of porphyrins within a transparent glass matrix has the potential to enhance their stability, particularly by providing a protective environment that shields the porphyrin molecules from external factors that could induce degradation, while allowing the exploitation of the optical properties. The nature of a glass matrices can offer several advantages in this regard. Firstly, the glass network can act as a physical barrier, isolating the porphyrin molecules from harsh reaction conditions or environmental factors such as oxygen, moisture, or reactive species. Secondly, the inherent stability of glass materials against chemical corrosion and thermal decomposition can help maintain the integrity of the porphyrin molecules over extended periods. However, the effectiveness of this approach would depend on the compatibility between the porphyrin and glass components, the method of incorporation, and whether or not a controlled spatial incorporation is possible without harming the chromophore molecules.

On the other hand, phosphate glasses are popular due to their

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versatile properties that include among other low glass transition temperatures [24,25], photochromic effect [26], second harmonic generation platforms [27] and high thermal expansion coefficients [28]. Also, phosphate glasses have been utilized in the development of optical fibers [29], waveguides, and lasers, exploiting their excellent optical properties for efficient light transmission and manipulation. Additionally, their ion-conducting properties [30] make them suitable candidates for solid electrolytes in batteries and fuel cells, while due to their biocompatibility bioactive phosphate glasses have been used in biomedical applications [31–33].

In this study, we demonstrate for the first time the encapsulation of molecular chromophores within silver phosphate (AgPO_3) glass by means of a simple, fast, low-temperature, post-glass quenching method. Based on the developed synthesis procedure, the vitrification of porphyrin molecules on the surfaces of glass samples was achieved, offering them stability protection, while allowing the light optoelectronic interactions with the surroundings, i.e. rendering them suitable for catalysis applications. The AgPO_3 glass was selected as a protection medium because of its soft nature, low glass transition temperature ($T_g = 192^\circ\text{C}$), transparency in most of the visible region, easy preparation, and low-toxicity nature [25]. Based on this approach, one of the most simple porphyrins, 5,10,15,20-Tetraphenyl-21H,23H-porphine (TPP), is vitrified into the glass matrix following the initial glass quenching. This novel approach introduces a significant advancement in enabling the confined spatial positioning of chromophores within the surface of a transparent medium, while utilizing only low-temperature glass melting procedures, i.e. below 200°C . Noteworthy, this approach does not require any additional means such as anchoring groups, which would demand further synthetic modifications. Furthermore, the described post-glass quenching encapsulation process is cost-effective while diminishing structural degradation of the porphyrin, upon encapsulation. The developed composite porphyrin-glasses are investigated towards their stability against visible light exposure as well as the maintenance of their self-assembled architectures.

2. Experimental

2.1. Material synthesis

All reagents were purchased from common commercial sources and used without any further purification, unless otherwise stated. 5,10,15,20-Tetraphenyl-21H,23H-porphine (TPP) was synthesized following the Alder-Longo method [34]. TPP was fully characterized via ^1H and ^{13}C NMR as well as Absorption and Emission spectroscopies (Figs S1–S3). Silver metaphosphate glass (AgPO_3) was synthesized using AgNO_3 (99.995 %) and $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ (99.999 %) as starting materials following known experimental procedures [25,35–37].

For the post-melting encapsulation of molecular porphyrin molecules we followed a well-established approach [25]. Fig. 1 illustrates the fabrication procedure that was followed for the preparation of the porphyrin glasses. Initially the pristine AgPO_3 glass substrate was heated at 65°C and 1 mL of TPP in THF (2.5 mg/mL) was drop-casted on top (drop-casted sample, Fig. S4). After the solvent evaporation the temperature was gradually increased to the transition temperature of AgPO_3 , i.e. 192°C for 5 min. The glass gained significant viscosity which allowed the smooth vitrification of the porphyrin layer within the AgPO_3 network (annealed sample, Fig. S4). Total immersion of the porphyrin layer was achieved via the splat-quenching the upper surface of the sample using a silicon wafer (encapsulated sample, Fig. S4). Splat-quenching was achieved by pressing a silicon wafer on top of the upper face of the AgPO_3 glass while kept on the hot-plate at 192°C . Afterwards the silicon wafer was removed and the composite glass was let to cool to room temperature. The results presented in this work are indicative data from repeating the experiment many times under lab ambient, without observing any differences in the structural and optical properties of the so-formed composite glasses.

Fig. 1. Schematic animation of the fabrication procedure of porphyrin glasses, drop-casted on, annealed on and encapsulated in AgPO_3 .

2.2. Materials characterization

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy: The porphyrin moieties were analyzed with ^1H NMR spectroscopy using Bruker AMX-500 MHz spectrometer. All measurements were carried out at room temperature in a deuterated solvent using residual protons as internal reference. **Ultraviolet–visible (UV–vis) absorption spectroscopy:** In all studies, spectrometer Shimadzu UV-1700 was used. The reported experiments were performed using quartz cuvettes of 0.2 cm path-length. **Fluorescence emission spectroscopy:** The emission spectra were measured on a JASCO FP-6500 fluorescence spectrophotometer equipped with a red-sensitive WRE-343 photomultiplier tube (wavelength range: 200–850 nm). **Scanning Electron Microscopy:** Field-emission scanning electron microscope (JEOL, JSM-7000F) equipped with an INCA PentaFET-x3 EDS detector was used to record the SEM images. **Raman Spectroscopy:** A Nicolet Almega XR Micro Raman analysis system equipped with a diode-pumped solid-state laser (DPSS) was used. Excitation wavelength was 473 nm. For the photodegradation experiments a white LED lamp 40 W was utilized and placed at 10 cm distance from each porphyrin-glass sample. Each samples contained the same porphyrin quantity (1 mg of TPP).

3. Results and discussion

The incorporation of porphyrin chromophores to the phosphate network, alters the optical properties of the composite glasses. As reported from previous studies, the pristine binary AgPO_3 glass is almost transparent, down to 380 nm [28]. Rather differently, the UV–Vis absorption spectra of the developed porphyrin- AgPO_3 glasses exhibit all characteristic peaks of the porphyrin components additional to the phosphate glass band (Fig. 2a, Fig S5a). More specifically, for the TPP encapsulated in AgPO_3 we observed the glass absorption bellow 350 nm, the porphyrin Soret band at 438 nm (which is attributed to the molecular $\text{S}_0 \rightarrow \text{S}_2$ transition) as well as the porphyrin Q-bands at after the post melting encapsulation. This observation is further supported by the fluorescence emission studies (Fig. 2b–S5b). In general, free base porphyrins in tetrahydrofuran exhibit a typical $\text{S}_1 \rightarrow \text{S}_0$ emission at 650 nm and 715 nm for Q (0,0) and Q (1,0) transitions. However, both in solid state and in the AgPO_3 glass matrix, the two-band pattern is altered and shows a red shift in the emission spectra together with an additional emission maximum at 755 nm. This observation has been previously reported and explained on the basis of changes in planarity [38]. Other

Fig. 2. a) UV-Vis absorption spectra and b) fluorescence emission spectra after excitation at 525 nm, of TPP in solid state and TPP encapsulated in AgPO_3 .

possible explanation derives from the self-aggregation of the porphyrin molecules utilizing π - π supramolecular interactions [39]. Notably the differences between the absorption spectra in solid (Fig. 2a) and solution (Fig. S5a) are also attributed aggregation phenomena derived from non-covalent interactions [40–42]. Remarkably, these results show that the inclusion of porphyrin molecules within the phosphate glass induces impressive photoluminescence properties to the composite glasses. It is emphasized that such a photoluminescence profile is totally absent from the spectrum of the pristine AgPO_3 glass [25].

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) studies were conducted to establish the self-assembly mode of the porphyrin molecules, as well as their spatial vitrification in the AgPO_3 glass. Fig. 3a depicts SEM image of the TPP sample annealed at 192 °C, while Fig. 3b presents the corresponding cross-sectional image upon splat-quenching the TPP within the surface of the glass substrate. As illustrated in Fig. 3a, TPP self-

assembles into rectangular nanostructures which either remain in the surface of the substrate (drop-casted sample) or are vitrified within AgPO_3 (annealed sample). The obtained self-assembling motif could be the result of the elevated temperature during the solvent evaporation (65 °C) for the sample preparation [43]. Further immersion of the TPP layer was achieved via the splat-quenching as verified in Fig. 3b. The porphyrin molecules lay approximately 20 μm within the AgPO_3 matrix according to Fig. 3b and this was further evidenced by Raman spectroscopy studies in Fig. 3c and d. Notably the thickness of the deposited porphyrin layer is around $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ as revealed by the SEM (Fig. 3b). SEM/EDS analysis on the encapsulated TPP in the AgPO_3 glass was performed to enhance the information about the elemental compositions and confirmed the presence of carbon derived from TPP molecules which was absent in the pristine AgPO_3 sample (Fig. S6, Table S1). TGA curves diagrams of pristine AgPO_3 and encapsulated TPP in AgPO_3 are

Fig. 3. SEM image of TPP a) annealed on AgPO_3 and b) encapsulated in AgPO_3 , Raman spectra at different z axis depths of TPP c) annealed on AgPO_3 and d) encapsulated in AgPO_3 .

presented in Fig. S7 and show that the encapsulated sample displayed an additional weight loss of $\sim 1.5\%$ which corresponds to the weight % of the porphyrin in the encapsulated material. XRD measurements of the pristine and encapsulated samples were performed and verified the amorphous nature of both materials (Fig. S8).

Raman spectroscopy was employed to probe any structural modifications of the phosphate glass network, upon the porphyrin encapsulation. Fig. S9 presents the room temperature Raman spectrum of the pristine AgPO_3 glass, the molecular TPP and the corresponding spectra of the composite porphyrin glass. The two main Raman features shown in Fig. S9 are distinct signatures of such structural units of AgPO_3 glass network. In particular, the key band at $\text{ca. } 1140\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the symmetric stretching vibration of terminal PO_2^- groups, whereas the broader band at $\text{ca. } 675\text{ cm}^{-1}$ originates from the symmetric stretching movement of P–O–P bridges within the phosphate backbone [44]. Notably, inspection of Fig. S9 as well as Fig. 3c and d, reveals that the incorporation of the porphyrin layer leaves both AgPO_3 Raman bands unaffected since neither their position nor their relative intensity is changed. This observation implies that in the composite glasses, the encapsulation of porphyrin molecules has no effect on the connectivity of the phosphate glass network. The spectra of Fig. 3c and d are normalized at the strongest band at 1140 cm^{-1} in order to facilitate comparison. Importantly, Fig. 3c shows that TPP is mainly located on the surface of the annealed sample since all characteristic peaks, i.e. the wagging of the phenyl Hs at $\text{ca. } 825\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the $\text{C}_m\text{-C}_p$ bond stretching at 1234 cm^{-1} and the asymmetric stretching and bending deformation of the $\text{C}_a\text{-C}_m\text{-C}_a$ at $\text{ca. } 1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$, are more intense at $0\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ depth [45]. While going deeper in the annealed sample, these peaks diminish, and the Raman spectra resemble only the two key peaks of the AgPO_3 glass. On the contrary, in case of the encapsulated sample the TPP bands are more intense at the encapsulation at nearly $20\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ within the AgPO_3 matrix (Fig. 3d). These results are in direct alignment with the SEM observations and prove the concept of confined spatial positioning of porphyrin chromophores within a transparent (in the visible region) glass medium using only post-melting encapsulation procedure.

We move on now to consider the photoinduced stability against photodegradation of the developed composite TPP-glasses towards their potential employment in light harvesting applications, where a common issue is the decomposition of the photosensitizer. In order to demonstrate the improved stability of the vitrified TPP molecules, we

performed stability tests by irradiating each sample with a white LED lamp 40 W at 10 cm distance while recording SEM images and fluorescence emission spectra before and after the irradiation [46–48]. Fig. 4 depicts the SEM images before and after irradiation using a white LED lamp 40 W at 10 cm distance of the drop casted, the annealed and the encapsulated sample. As illustrated in Fig. 4 the self-assembled architectures of the drop-casted sample (Fig. 4a) are completely destroyed after 10 min of irradiation (Fig. 4d). Such photodegradation behavior is expected for free-base porphyrins [20]. However, when porphyrin molecules are vitrified (annealed sample) or encapsulated in the AgPO_3 glass network, their rectangular architectures are substantially retained (Fig. 4b, c, 4e and 4f). Noteworthy the post-melting encapsulation process does not affect the rectangular self-assembled architectures due to the significant viscosity that AgPO_3 gained at $192\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ which allowed the smoothed vitrification before the splat-quenching process.

In order to measure the stability against photodegradation we recorded the photoluminescence before and after irradiation (Fig. 5). As explained above the additional emission maximum at 755 nm derives from the self-aggregation of the porphyrin molecules utilizing $\pi\text{-}\pi$ supramolecular interactions, while the emission at $\sim 660\text{ nm}$ and $\sim 730\text{ nm}$ for $\text{Q}_x(0,0)$ and $\text{Q}_x(1,0)$ transitions from $\text{S}_1 \rightarrow \text{S}_0$ [38,39]. Since in all samples the amount of porphyrin was the same we can clearly conclude from Fig. 5a that both thermal annealing and encapsulation enhance significantly the porphyrin photoluminescence compared to the simple drop-casted sample. This can be explained from the presence of Ag nanoparticles within AgPO_3 glass matrix which induce increased light scattering effects [25,36,37]. After irradiation we observe the same emission intensity trend between the three samples (Fig. 5b). Importantly the peak at 755 nm diminishes almost completely for the drop-casted sample, which is in accordance with the SEM observations where the self-assembled structures were also completely destroyed after the irradiation (Fig. 4d).

In an effort to quantify the stability under light exposure we calculated the emission peak intensity ratio $\frac{755\text{ nm (attributed to self-assembled molecules)}}{730\text{ nm (attributed to monomeric molecules)}}$ and the values are summarized in Table 1. We employed this approach as a quantitative spectroscopic tool to “measure” how much the self-assembled nanostructures are retained in these systems. It is clearly observed that both annealed TPP on glass and encapsulated TPP within the glass exhibited improved photoluminescence stability when compared to the reference drop casted

Fig. 4. SEM images before and after irradiation from a white LED lamp 40 W at 10 cm distance of TPP a,d) drop casted on AgPO_3 b,e) annealed on AgPO_3 and c,f) encapsulated in AgPO_3 .

Fig. 5. Fluorescence emission spectra before (a) and after (b) irradiation of three TPP samples: drop casted on AgPO_3 , annealed on AgPO_3 and encapsulated in AgPO_3 .

Table 1

Summary of emission peak intensity ratios at 755 nm over 730 nm. These data include the mean values and standard deviation from 5 samples.

Ratio 755/730 nm:	Before irradiation	After irradiation	Decrease
Drop casted	1.12	0.61	46 % \pm 4 %
Annealed	1.58	1.15	27 % \pm 3 %
Encapsulated	1.68	1.49	11 % \pm 2 %

sample. Notably the stability was better for the annealed sample and the best for the encapsulated one, which is desired for photonic applications. Additionally, the enhanced stability of the annealed sample leads the way for improved performance in various photocatalytic applications, where direct interaction with other catalytic components is necessary, since it will allow interface with the catalytic medium.

Conclusions

In summary, herein we demonstrated a simple and low temperature post-glass quenching method for the development of composite porphyrin glasses by incorporating pre-synthesized molecular chromophores within transparent phosphate glasses. The proposed method enables controlled spatial positioning of the porphyrin layer within the glass matrix. Additionally, this simple post-melting encapsulation method ensures that the optical and electronic properties of porphyrins remain intact, rendering the developed composite porphyrin-glasses suitable for photocatalytic applications. The developed composite TPP-glasses exhibit remarkable stability against visible light exposure when compared to the drop-casted porphyrin layers on the surface of the AgPO_3 glass. Importantly, the glass encapsulation resolves the necessity of anchoring moieties in light harvesting applications utilizing molecular chromophores and/or catalysts. The described vitrification procedure is proven to be suitable for stabilizing the porphyrin self-assembled nanostructures within a transparent visible optical medium, while the assembled architectures can be easily modified according to the needs of the targeted application by simply altering the self-assembly conditions. Based on the above, the presented synthesis route is expected to open up new ways towards the development of advanced composite porphyrin glass architectures for various photocatalytic applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Emmanouil Nikoloudakis: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ioannis Konidakis:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Harris Goniotakis:** Investigation, Data curation. **Eleni Agapaki:** Investigation,

Data curation. **Klytaimnitra Katsara:** Data curation. **George Kenakakis:** Methodology, Conceptualization. **Athanasios G. Coutsolelos:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Emmanuel Stratakis:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Emmanuel Stratakis reports financial support was provided by Institute of Electronic Structure and Laser. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix ASupplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2025.116952>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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